

Notes

Diorganotin(IV) Chelates of naturally occurring Hydroxynaphthoquinones

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Quinones and their substituted derivatives have long been known to possess numerous chemically and biologically significant properties with many important applications in several areas¹. Hydroxynaphthoquinones and their chelation with various metal ions increase their activity tremendously. The organotin(IV) complexes of juglone displayed more antibacterial activity than the free ligands². Since in most of the applications of hydroxyquinones, their chelating ability plays an important role, the study of their metal chelates has been of great interest in understanding mechanisms of their chemical and biological activities. Consequently during the last two decades, several papers concerning the synthesis, characterisation, thermal stability, kinetic studies and biological function of some metal chelates of hydroxyquinones, hydroxynaphthoquinones have been published³.

It seems that no study has been reported on the complexes of lawsone (1), lapachol (2), juglone (3) plumbagin (4) and in the present communication our results concerning their chelates with tetravalent tin metal are presented.

- 1; R¹=OH, R²=H, R³=H
- 2; R¹=OH, R²=CH₂CH=C(CH₃)₂, R³=H
- 3; R¹=R²=H, R³=OH
- 4; R¹=CH₃, R²=H, R³=OH

Results and Discussion

All the chelates were obtained as fine powder or microcrystalline solids (Table 1), soluble in acetone, methylene chloride and alcohol. The chelates gave satisfactory elemental analyses and their structures were determined on the basis of spectroscopic measurements.

The uv-visible spectra (EtOH) of the free ligands showed mainly three bands at 220–250, 266–278 and 333–420 nm attributable to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ (benzenoid) and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ (quinonoid) transitions respectively. In the spectra of the chelates, the first band remained unchanged. The second band shifted towards lower energy at 262–284 nm. In the region 416–436 nm, a new band appeared which was absent in the spectra of the free ligands, and hence can be assigned to M→L type transitions⁴.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Yield %
Lawsone (1) chelates :			
Me ₂ SnL ₂	Orange	250	72
Bu ₂ SnL ₂	Orange	285	81
Ph ₂ SnL ₂	Red	260	55
Lapachol (2) chelates :			
Me ₂ SnL ₂	Brownish red	210	77
Bu ₂ SnL ₂	Dark red	157	62
Ph ₂ SnL ₂	Orange red	210	60
Juglone (3) chelates :			
Me ₂ SnL ₂	Cherry red	182	78
Bu ₂ SnL ₂	Brownish red	197	70
Plumbagin (4) chelates :			
Me ₂ SnL ₂	Brown	190	79
Ph ₂ SnL ₂	Dark green	172	79

The most relevant bands in the ir spectra of the chelates and their tentative assignments are shown in Table 2. The absorption around 3 200 cm⁻¹ due to phenolic hydroxyl group in the free ligands was absent in all the chelates indicating the chelation through hydroxyl group.

The non-coordinated carbonyls $\nu_{C=O}$ (free) in all the complexes occurred at 1 670–1 630 cm⁻¹. The stretching frequency $\nu_{C=O}$ of the non-coordinated carbonyl group in all the chelates is similar to that of the free ligands⁴. The coordinated carbonyl groups in all the chelates appeared at lower energy at 1 625–1 610 cm⁻¹ as strong band. This observation can be easily explained on the basis of the structure 5 for the ligands 1 and 4 chelates and structure 6 for those of 2 and 3 chelates. In these structures, the ligand acts through its monomeric form as a chelating bidentate ligand, forming a chelated ring with the metal ion.

The absorptions in the region $1580-1550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are due to normal aromatic vibrations and the one around 1320 cm^{-1} of medium intensity is due to the activating effects of the carbonyl groups on the adjacent C—C vibrations. The strong to medium absorptions at $1290-1230\text{ cm}^{-1}$, found to be present in all hydroxynaphthoquinones and in their chelates, are characteristic of quinone compounds. The intense C—O stretching absorption occurring in the quinones around 1220 cm^{-1} appeared only as a shoulder in these chelates confirming the involvement of C-2 or C-5 hydroxyls in chelation. The olefinic C—H wagging mode⁸ appeared in all the complexes around 1000 cm^{-1} and the adjacent hydrogens of aromatic ring appeared at $865-730\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The band at $490-430\text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been assigned to $\nu_{\text{Sn-O}}$ symmetric stretching vibrations. The ν_{Sym} (Sn—C) and ν_{Asy} (Sn—C) vibrations are assigned in the regions $510-530$ and $545-580\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively, by comparison with ir spectra of the corresponding alkoxides and oxygen donor ligands⁸ thus clearly indicating distorted octahedral structures for all these chelates.

5; R = H or Me
R' = Me, n-Bu, Ph

6; R = H or $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}=\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$
R' = Me, n-Bu, Ph

The main feature of the pmr spectral studies of the chelates was the absence of phenolic hydroxyl protons at $\delta 7.4-12.5$ thereby suggesting chelation through C₂ or C₅ hydroxyl group and supplementing structures 5 and 6. Some salient features of pmr spectra of the diorganotin-quinolates (Table 1) are the tin-methyl protons in case of dimethyltin chelates appeared in the range $\delta 0.7-1.0$ as singlets

whereas in the case of the dibutyltin complexes, the alkyltin protons were observed at $\delta 0.8-2.00$ as multiplets. A multiplet at $\delta 7.3-7.4$ was associated with the tin-phenyl protons of diphenyltin diquinolates. In lapachol chelates (Table 1), the sidechain alkenyl protons were observed at $\delta 1.62-1.91$ (s, CH₃), $3.24-3.50$ (d, $J 7\text{ Hz}$, CH₂), $5.16-5.34$ (t, $J 7\text{ Hz}$, =CH). In case of dimethyltin diplumbagin (Me₂SnL₂), the methyl protons attached to quinonoid ring appeared as singlet at $\delta 2.14$. In all the chelates, the quinonoid protons were attributed to singlets appearing at $\delta 6.37-7.0$. The aromatic protons of the quinonoid rings appeared as two sets of multiplets at $\delta 7.3-7.8$ and $7.7-8.3$.

All these observations thus confirm the structures 5 and 6 for these chelates.

The ¹³C nmr spectrum (CDCl₃) of dimethyltin dilapacholate (Me₂SnL₂) was compared with ¹³C nmr of the ligand⁷. It was noticed that the coordinated carbonyl carbon at C-1 shifted from $\delta 181.5$ ppm in ligand to $\delta 135.8$ ppm in the chelate. Whereas the C-2 hydroxyl carbon shifted from $\delta 155.4$ to 136.3 ppm.

Experimental

The organotin(IV) chelates of the quinones were synthesised by the reaction of dimethyltin, di-n-butyltin and diphenyltin diisopropoxides with lawsone, lapachol, juglone and plumbagin. Owing to the highly oxidisable and extremely hydrolyzable nature of organotin alkoxides, all the reactions were carried out under dry nitrogen. All the reagents were dried and purified by fractionation or distillation before use. Alkoxides of organotin were prepared and purified by the standard methods⁸. Naturally occurring hydroxynaphthoquinones used as ligands are 2-hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone (lawsone) (1), 2-hydroxy-3-(3-methyl-2-butenyl)-1,4-naphthoquinone (lapachol) (2), 5-hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone (juglone) (3) and 5-hydroxy-2-methyl-1,4-naphthoquinone (plumbagin) (4). Lapachol was isolated in sufficient amount from the plant *Tectona grandis*⁹. Lawsone, juglone and plumbagin were procured from Aldrich.

The analyses of tin was carried out by standard method¹⁰. Isopropanol was estimated by the oxidimetric method¹¹. The ir spectra (KBr/ncat) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 or Beckmann IR-9 spectrophotometers and pmr and ¹³C nmr spectra were on a Jeol FX90 QFT spectrometer at 90 MHz and 5 KHz respectively.

Preparation of complexes: To a solution of diorganotin dialkoxide in benzene, was added a benzene solution of the appropriate ligand quinone in the stoichiometric ratio of 1 : 2. The reaction mixture was refluxed under a fractionating column at bath temperature and the liberated isopropanol was fractionated azeotropically over a period of

TABLE 2—IR SPECTRAL DATA (cm⁻¹) OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	(C=O) (free)	(C=O) (chelated)	(C=C)	(C—O)	ν_{as} (Sn—C)	ν_s (Sn—C)	(Sn—O)
Lawsone chelates :							
Lawsone	1 655s	1 620sh	1 575s	1 280m 1 260m	—	—	—
Me ₂ SnL ₂	1 640sh	1 620s	1 580s 1 555s	1 260m 1 1240s	580m	508w	490m
Bu ₂ SnL ₂	1 636sh	1 610m	1 570s	1 240m	550m	500w	425m
Ph ₂ SnL ₂	1 630sh	1 620s	1 580s	1 260s 1 235s	555w	507w	450m
Lapachol chelates :							
Lapachol	1 660s	1 630s	1 580s	1 275s	—	—	—
Me ₂ SnL ₂	1 636sh	1 625s	1 570s	1 260s	545m	520w	490mw
Bu ₂ SnL ₂	1 630s	1 610s	1 560m	1 270s 1 230s	560m	507w	445m
Ph ₂ SnL ₂	1 630s	1 625s	1 575s	1 260s	530w	507w	430m
Juglone chelates :							
Juglone	1 670s	1 647s	1 550s	1 220m	—	—	—
Me ₂ SnL ₂	1 645s	1 625s	1 585s 1 575m	1 235s	550w	530w	420m
Bu ₂ SnL ₂	1 665s	1 640s	1 600s	1 240m	545w	510w	450w
Plumbagin chelates :							
Me ₂ SnL ₂	1 645s	1 620s	1 580s	1 240s	545m	520mw	440m
Ph ₂ SnL ₂	1 655s	1 625s	1 590s	1 280s	550w	510w	445m

3—5 h. After complete removal of isopropanol, the excess solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the resulting solids were crystallised from benzene or benzene-hexane (1 : 1) mixture.

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